

DYNAMIC FAILURE OF BIMATERIALS AND COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Some results of high speed interferometric measurements on dynamically propagating interfacial cracks are presented. PMMA/Steel bimaterial specimens of the three point bend type are used. Issues regarding data analysis are discussed. The effects of the near-tip three-dimensionality are analyzed. In addition the interpretation of the obtained interferograms using transient elastodynamic crack tip fields is seen to be necessary for the accurate analysis of optical data obtained in this study. Finally a preliminary report on the dynamic failure of composite laminates is presented.

Keywords : Transient dynamic fracture, Bimaterial interfaces, Composite laminates, 3-D effects.

1. INTRODUCTION

The scientific understanding of the mechanics of crack initiation and growth in bimaterial interfaces is essential for the effective study of failure processes in advanced materials such as composites. This understanding includes the behavior of interfacial cracks under many kinds of loading, ranging from quasistatic to dynamic. Although in recent years we have seen considerable research activity on issues regarding the quasistatic failure of bimaterials, very little work has been done on their response to dynamic loads. Due to the complexity of the problem, only a few theoretical studies of specific problems have been made ([1-3]). In addition very little experimentation has been done on the subject.

In this paper we shall present some dynamic experiments on bimaterial specimens. The method of CGS coupled with high speed photography will be used to obtain real time images of the fracture process near the crack tip. Analysis of the images will be done using the asymptotic steady state elastodynamic analysis provided by Yang, Suo and Shih [4] and the transient analysis of Liu, Rosakis and Lambros [5]. The existence of a near-tip three-dimensional region and its effects on data analysis will also be discussed. Finally a preliminary plan for dynamic experiments of thick fiber reinforced polymeric plates will be described.

2. COHERENT GRADIENT SENSING (TRANSMISSION)

Consider a planar wavefront normally incident on an optically and mechanically isotropic, transparent plate of initial uniform thickness h and refractive index n . The specimen occupies the (x_1, x_2) plane in the undeformed configuration. (See fig. 1). If the plate is deformed, the transmitted wave front will be expressed as $S(x_1, x_2, x_3) = x_3 + \Delta S(x_1, x_2) = \text{const}$, where ΔS is the optical path change acquired during refraction. As discussed in detail by Rosakis [6], ΔS is related to the deformation state by the relation,

$$\Delta S(x_1, x_2) = 2h(n-1) \int_0^{x_3/h} \epsilon_{33} d(x_3/h) + 2h \int_0^{x_3/h} \Delta n d(x_3/h). \quad (1)$$

The first term of eq. (1) represents the net optical path difference due to the plate thickness change caused by the strain component ϵ_{33} . The second term is due to the stress induced change of refractive index of the material. This change in the refractive index Δn is given by the Maxwell relation

$$\Delta n = D_1(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}),$$

where D_1 is the stress optic coefficient and σ_{ij} are Cartesian components of the stress tensor. The above relation is strictly true for isotropic linear elastic solids. For such solids the strain component ϵ_{33} can also be related to the stress and equation (1) then becomes :

$$\Delta S(x_1, x_2) = 2hc_\sigma \int_0^{t/2} \left\{ (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22}) \left[1 - D_2 \left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{\nu(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22})} \right) \right] \right\} dx_3/h, \quad (2)$$

where

$$c_\sigma = \left[D_1 - \frac{\nu}{E}(n-1) \right],$$

$$D_2 = - \left[\frac{\nu D_1 + \frac{\nu(n-1)}{E}}{D_1 \frac{\nu(n-1)}{E}} \right],$$

E , ν and c_σ are the Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and the stress optical coefficient of the material respectively.

The CGS set-up described below is sensitive to in-plane gradients of optical path changes $\Delta S(x_1, x_2)$.

2.1. The Experimental Set-up

A schematic of the experimental apparatus is shown in figure 1. When the transmitted wave front emerges from the specimen after refraction, it is processed by a pair of high density gratings, G_1 and G_2 separated by a distance Δ . In a typical set-up, the gratings have their rulings parallel to either the x_1 or x_2 directions. The grating pitch is denoted by p . The action of the gratings is to displace (shear) the diffracted beam and recombine it with itself, thus creating an interferogram after G_2 .

Figure 1 : Schematic of the experimental set-up for transmission CGS.

The light emerging from G_2 is collected by the filtering lens L_1 and its frequency content (diffraction spots) is displayed on its back focal plane. By locating a filtering aperture around either the ± 1 diffraction orders, information regarding the gradient components of $\Delta S(x_1, x_2)$ along either the x_1 or x_2 axis is obtained on the image plane. The camera is kept focused on the specimen plane. For grating rulings perpendicular to the x_α axis the resulting fringe pattern is proportional to $\partial(\Delta S)/\partial x_\alpha$, $\alpha=(1,2)$.

More specifically, and as demonstrated by a first order analysis described by Tippur, Krishnaswamy and Rosakis [7] or a higher order Fourier optics analysis by Lee, Lambros and Rosakis [8], the resulting fringes can be related to gradients of $\Delta S(x_1, x_2)$ as follows :

$$\frac{\partial(\Delta S)}{\partial x_\alpha} = \frac{k_\alpha p}{\Delta}, \quad \alpha = (1,2), \quad (3)$$

where

$$k_\alpha = \begin{cases} m & \text{for } \alpha = 1, m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \\ n & \text{for } \alpha = 2, n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \end{cases}$$

and m and n are the fringe orders for the x_1, x_2 gradient contours respectively.

2.2. Influence of Three-Dimensionality on Data Analysis

The discussion of the previous section was intentionally kept as general as possible within the assumptions of isotropic linear elasticity. For either a homogeneous or a bimaterial cracked linear elastic plate of uniform thickness and finite in-plane dimensions, the optical path difference (transparent side of specimen) in general will depend on the details of the three-dimensional elastostatic or elastodynamic stress state that would exist at the vicinity of the crack tip. This would be a function of the applied loading, as well as of the in-plane dimensions and thickness of the specimen. For bimaterial systems it is also expected to depend on material mismatch.

Given the lack of full field, three-dimensional analytical solutions in fracture mechanics, experimental information can strictly be extracted by means of detailed numerical calculations. Nevertheless, there exist certain non-trivial special cases for which available asymptotic solutions, based on two-dimensional analyses, may provide adequate approximations for $\Delta S(x_1, x_2)$ at certain regions near the crack tip. In particular, it has been argued that conditions of plane stress will dominate in thin, *homogeneous* cracked plates at distances from the crack front larger than half the specimen thickness. This would imply that if only data outside the three-dimensional zone are analyzed the results could be interpreted on the basis of a plane stress analysis, see Rosakis and Ravi-Chandar [9].

To illustrate the extent of near-tip three-dimensionality in *bimaterial* plates, reference is made to figure 2 which shows contours of the quantity $\sigma_{33}/\nu(\sigma_{11}+\sigma_{22})$ for a three point bend bimaterial specimen. This ratio also appears in the second term of the integrand of the optical path difference relation (2). The ratio is often called the degree of plane strain. It is a measure of near-tip three-dimensionality and is obtained by means of a 3-D finite element calculation which models a stationary crack in a three point bend PMMA/aluminum specimen subjected to dynamic loading. In regions where the deformation approaches plane strain like conditions this ratio approaches the value of 1. Figure 2 gives a 3-D view of the PMMA side of the bond which is relevant for the analysis of transmission CGS patterns. As is obvious from this figure, the three-dimensional zone extends along the PMMA-Al bond line. Unlike the homogeneous case [10] there exists no plane stress region at any visible distance directly ahead of the crack tip. Here, plane stress conditions are achieved above a strip of height roughly equal to $0.4h$ lying ahead of the crack tip in the PMMA side. In addition there exists a narrow wedge of plane stress defined by $100^\circ < \theta < 150^\circ$, $r < 0.1h$. (For details see Lee and Rosakis [11]).

Figure 2 : Three dimensional contour plot of the degree of plane strain for a PMMA/Al bond. The PMMA side is visible here.

For points outside the 3-D region, a plane stress approximation will be applicable ($\sigma_{33}/v(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22}) \rightarrow 0$). Indeed for such points the optical path difference ΔS in (2) will simplify to :

$$\Delta S(x_1, x_2) \approx c_\sigma h [\hat{\sigma}_{11}(x_1, x_2) + \hat{\sigma}_{22}(x_1, x_2)], \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\sigma}_{11}$ and $\hat{\sigma}_{22}$ are *thickness averages* of the stress components in the plate.

Thus for points outside the near-tip three-dimensional region the CGS patterns assume the a simple interpretation in terms of 2-D stress field approximations. In particular, eqs (3) and (4) now indicate that the fringes obtained from regions surrounding the 3-D zone can be related to the in-plane gradients of $\hat{\sigma}_{11} + \hat{\sigma}_{22}$ as follows :

$$c_\sigma h \frac{\partial(\hat{\sigma}_{11} + \hat{\sigma}_{22})}{\partial x_1} = \frac{mp}{\Delta},$$

or

$$c_\sigma h \frac{\partial(\hat{\sigma}_{11} + \hat{\sigma}_{22})}{\partial x_2} = \frac{np}{\Delta}, \quad (5)$$

where in the case of a transmission c_σ is the stress optical coefficient of PMMA.

3. DATA ANALYSIS USING 2-D ASYMPTOTIC THEORY

Relations (5) can be used to estimate fracture parameters from points outside the 3-D zone. One could expect that the plane stress region surrounding the crack near-tip three-dimensional region would be well described by the most singular term in the asymptotic expansion for stress, i.e. that a K -dominant region would somewhere around the crack tip. This is something to be verified though and should not be taken for granted, especially in regions relatively far from the crack tip or in experiments showing transient effects (eg rapidly changing crack tip velocity). In such cases the fields around the crack tip may be better described by a higher order analyses.

For cracks propagating dynamically under steady state conditions in bimaterial specimens, Yang, Suo and Shih [4] observed that near the crack tip the stress field assumes the form :

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta} = Re\left\{\frac{K^d r^{i\varepsilon}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}}\right\}\bar{\sigma}_{\alpha\beta}^{(1)}(\theta, \dot{a}) + Im\left\{\frac{K^d r^{i\varepsilon}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}}\right\}\bar{\sigma}_{\alpha\beta}^{(2)}(\theta, \dot{a}), \quad (6)$$

where r, θ are polar coordinates of a coordinate system translating with the crack tip at speed \dot{a} and $K^d = K_1^d + iK_2^d$ is the *complex dynamic* stress intensity factor. The material mismatch parameter $\varepsilon = \hat{\varepsilon}(\dot{a})$ is now a function of crack tip speed and of the moduli of the materials of the bimaterial combination. Analytical expressions for $\bar{\sigma}_{\alpha\beta}^{(1)}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{\alpha\beta}^{(2)}$ are given by Yang, Suo and Shih [4].

By using equation (6) and after some algebraic manipulation $\hat{\sigma}_{11} + \hat{\sigma}_{22}$ can be written as :

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\sigma}_{11} + \hat{\sigma}_{22} = \frac{A}{\sqrt{2\pi r_i}} & \left[(1 + \alpha_s^2 - 2\eta\alpha_s) e^{\varepsilon(\pi - \theta_i)} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_i}{2} - \phi - \varepsilon \ln r_i\right) \right. \\ & \left. + (1 + \alpha_s^2 + 2\eta\alpha_s) e^{-\varepsilon(\pi - \theta_i)} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_i}{2} + \phi + \varepsilon \ln r_i\right) \right], \quad r \rightarrow 0, \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq \pi, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \frac{(\alpha_i^2 - \alpha_s^2) |K^d|}{(4\alpha_i\alpha_s - (1 + \alpha_s^2)^2) \cosh(\varepsilon\pi)}, \\ \alpha_{i,s} &= \left(1 - \frac{\dot{a}^2}{c_{i,s}^2}\right)^{1/2}, \quad \theta_i = \tan^{-1}[(\alpha_i x_2) / x_1], \quad r_i = \sqrt{x_1^2 + \alpha_i^2 x_2^2}, \\ K^d(t) &= K_1^d(t) + iK_2^d(t), \quad \phi(t) = \tan^{-1}(K_2^d(t) / K_1^d(t)), \end{aligned}$$

and $c_{i,s}$ are the longitudinal and transverse wave speeds respectively and $\varepsilon = \hat{\varepsilon}(\dot{a})$, $\eta = \hat{\eta}(\dot{a})$, are functions of crack tip speed and of material properties. These functions are given by Yang, Suo and Shih [4] and are such that $\varepsilon \rightarrow \varepsilon_0$, $\eta \rightarrow 1$ as $\dot{a} \rightarrow 0$. The bimaterial constant ε_0 is called the "quasistatic" mismatch parameter and is given by :

$$\varepsilon_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \ln \left[\frac{k_1 + \frac{1}{I}}{\frac{\mu_1}{k_2} + \frac{1}{I}} \right],$$

where $k_i = (3 - \nu_i) / (1 + \nu_i)$ for plane stress and ν_i and μ_i are the Poisson's ratio and shear moduli for material-1 and -2 respectively.

The field quantity of interest in analyzing the CGS patterns for material-1 is $ch\partial(\hat{\sigma}_{11} + \hat{\sigma}_{22}) / \partial x_1$. By differentiating eq. (7) with respect to x_1 we have :

$$\begin{aligned}
ch \frac{\partial(\hat{\sigma}_{11} + \hat{\sigma}_{22})}{\partial x_1} = & \frac{chr_i^{-3/2} e^{-\varepsilon(\pi-\theta_i)} A}{2\sqrt{2\pi}} \left[-(1 + \alpha_s^2 - 2\eta\alpha_s) e^{2\varepsilon(\pi-\theta_i)} \cos\left(\frac{3\theta_l}{2} - \phi - \varepsilon \ln r\right) \right. \\
& - (1 + \alpha_s^2 + 2\eta\alpha_s) \cos\left(\frac{3\theta_l}{2} + \phi + \varepsilon \ln r\right) \\
& + 2\varepsilon(1 + \alpha_s^2 - 2\eta\alpha_s) e^{2\varepsilon(\pi-\theta_i)} \sin\left(\frac{3\theta_l}{2} - \phi - \varepsilon \ln r\right) \\
& \left. - 2\varepsilon(1 + \alpha_s^2 + 2\eta\alpha_s) \sin\left(\frac{3\theta_l}{2} + \phi + \varepsilon \ln r\right) \right], \quad (8)
\end{aligned}$$

where A is as defined in (7) and $0 \leq \theta \leq \pi$.

From the above discussion it becomes obvious that extraction of parameters like K^d is now possible *provided* that experimental data are gathered from a region near the moving crack tip characterized by the structure presented in eqs. (7) and (8). In a region not characterized by such a K -field, the use of a higher order analysis is mandated. Such an analysis for a transiently propagating interfacial crack has been provided by Liu, Rosakis and Lambros [5]. It has been shown that there the trace of the stress tensor under plane stress conditions is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22}}{2\mu(\alpha_t^2 - \alpha_s^2)} = & |A_0| \Sigma_0(r_i, \theta_i) r_i^{-1/2} + \frac{4\alpha_s}{\mu D(v)(1 + \omega_s)} |A_1| \cos \Phi(A_1) \\
& + \left[\dot{\varepsilon} \Sigma_0^{(d)}(r_i, \theta_i) (\ln r_i)^2 + \Sigma_0^{(l)}(r_i, \theta_i) \ln r_i + \Sigma_0^{(n)}(r_i, \theta_i) + |A_2| \Sigma_2(r_i, \theta_i) \right] r_i^{1/2} + O(r_i) \quad (9)
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\Sigma_0(r_i, \theta_i) = & a_0 e^{-\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} - \varepsilon \ln r_i - \Phi(A_0)\right) + b_0 e^{\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} + \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(A_0)\right), \\
\Sigma_2(r_i, \theta_i) = & a_0 e^{-\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} + \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(A_2)\right) + b_0 e^{\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} - \varepsilon \ln r_i - \Phi(A_2)\right), \\
\Sigma_0^{(d)}(r_i, \theta_i) = & |\Omega_d| e^{-\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} + \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(\Omega_d)\right) - |\hat{\Omega}_d| e^{\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} - \varepsilon \ln r_i - \Phi(\hat{\Omega}_d)\right), \\
\Sigma_0^{(l)}(r_i, \theta_i) = & |A_i| e^{-\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} + \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(A_i)\right) - |\hat{A}_i| e^{\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} - \varepsilon \ln r_i - \Phi(\hat{A}_i)\right) \\
& + |B_i| e^{-\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{3\theta_l}{2} - \varepsilon \ln r_i - \Phi(B_i)\right) - |\hat{B}_i| e^{\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{3\theta_l}{2} + \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(\hat{B}_i)\right) \\
& - 2\dot{\varepsilon} \left[|\Omega_d| e^{-\varepsilon\theta} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} + \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(\Omega_d)\right) - |\hat{\Omega}_d| e^{\varepsilon\theta} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} - \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(\hat{\Omega}_d)\right) \right] \theta_i, \\
\Sigma_0^{(n)}(r_i, \theta_i) = & |A_n| e^{-\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} + \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(A_n)\right) - |\hat{A}_n| e^{\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} - \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(\hat{A}_n)\right) \\
& + |B_n| e^{-\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{3\theta_l}{2} - \varepsilon \ln r_i - \Phi(B_n)\right) - |\hat{B}_n| e^{\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{3\theta_l}{2} + \varepsilon \ln r_i - \Phi(\hat{B}_n)\right) \\
& + |C_n| e^{-\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{7\theta_l}{2} - \varepsilon \ln r_i - \Phi(C_n)\right) - |\hat{C}_n| e^{\varepsilon\theta} \cos\left(\frac{7\theta_l}{2} + \varepsilon \ln r_i - \Phi(\hat{C}_n)\right) \\
& - \left[|A_i| e^{-\varepsilon\theta} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} + \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(A_i)\right) - |\hat{A}_i| e^{\varepsilon\theta} \sin\left(\frac{\theta_l}{2} - \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(\hat{A}_i)\right) \right] \theta_i
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left[|B_i| e^{-\varepsilon \theta_i} \sin \left(\frac{3\theta_i}{2} - \varepsilon \ln r_i - \Phi(B_i) \right) - |\hat{B}_i| e^{\varepsilon \theta_i} \sin \left(\frac{3\theta_i}{2} + \varepsilon \ln r_i - \Phi(\hat{B}_i) \right) \right] \theta_i \\
& - \dot{\varepsilon} \left[|\Omega_d| e^{-\varepsilon \theta_i} \cos \left(\frac{\theta_i}{2} + \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(\Omega_d) \right) - |\hat{\Omega}_d| e^{\varepsilon \theta_i} \cos \left(\frac{\theta_i}{2} - \varepsilon \ln r_i + \Phi(\hat{\Omega}_d) \right) \right] \theta_i^2.
\end{aligned}$$

To apply this result to the analysis of a CGS interferogram, we need its x_I -gradient. This has been performed and the result is similar to eq. (9), only the orders of r_I have been decreased by 1 and the second term (constant) has disappeared. The x_I -gradient of eq. (9) contains 4 orders of r_I . These are : $r_i^{-3/2}$, $r_i^{-1/2} (\ln r)^2$, $r_i^{-1/2} \ln r$, $r_i^{-1/2}$. It also contains 28 undetermined constants. The two first constants $|A_0|$ and $\phi(A_0)$ are related to $|K^d|$ and ϕ (or K_I^d , K_2^d) of the Yang, Suo and Shih expression. In fact the most singular term of eq. (9) reduces to eq. (7). Under steady state conditions, eq. (9) reduces to an expression with 6 constants which are identical to the first 6 terms of the higher order steady state expansion derived by Deng [12]. Some of the new terms that appear in eq. (9) are those that exhibit a $r_i^{-1/2} (\ln r)^2$ and $r_i^{-1/2} \ln r$ radial dependence along with some changes in the coefficients of the $-1/2$ order. These terms are a result of the *transient* nature of crack growth. It is worth noting that most of these new terms are multiplied by the quantity $\dot{\varepsilon}$, the rate of change of the oscillatory index with time ($\dot{\varepsilon} = \frac{d\varepsilon}{dv} \frac{dv}{dt}$, $v = \dot{a}$ = speed). Thus, to a certain extent, $\dot{\varepsilon}$ is a measure of transience of the propagating crack. If $\dot{\varepsilon} = 0$ most, but not all transient terms disappear. Those that remain are those related to the rate of change of the complex stress intensity factor. Note that it is possible for $\dot{\varepsilon}$ to be small even if a large acceleration exists, if $d\varepsilon/dv$ is small. The variation of ε with velocity is shown in fig. 3. Whether or not $\dot{\varepsilon}$ can be used as reliable measure of transience will be investigated in a subsequent section.

Figure 3: Variation of the oscillatory index ε for a PMMA/Steel system with crack tip speed.

It is clear at this point that analysis of the fringe patterns obtained from a dynamic experiment can be made using either eq. (8) or the gradient of eq. (9). Which to use depends on whether a region of K -dominance can be established somewhere outside the near-tip three-dimensional region. Use of either equation allows estimation of the time variation of the relevant parameters. This is done by performing a least squares fitting procedure to data points digitized from the CGS interferograms obtained during an experiment. Of course the crack tip speed $a(t)$ is measured independently during each experiment.

4. DYNAMIC EXPERIMENTS ON BIMATERIAL INTERFACES

4.1 Bimaterial specimen preparation

Bimaterial specimens used in the dynamic experiments are of the three point or one point bending configuration (fig. 1). They are made from equal thickness sheets (thickness $h=9\text{mm}$) of commercially available poly-methylmethacrylate (PMMA)(material-1) and AISI 4340 steel (material-2). The two halves of the specimen are machined to ensure square edges and the bond face of the steel side is sandblasted using 10-20 μm size glass beads. Bond between the two materials is created using a commercially available (see Tippur and Rosakis [13]) methylmethacrylate monomer (MMA) which polymerizes at room temperature when mixed with a catalyst. This results in a bond material with stiffness characteristics similar to that of material-1. The steel part of the bond is coated with a thin layer of the mixture and held against the PMMA with a uniform pressure. The bond is then cured at room temperature for 24 hours and the resulting thickness is about 100 μm . A bond strength calibration experiment was also performed in [13]. It was seen there that a three point bend specimen made up of two PMMA halves glued using the above procedure had more than 95% the quasistatic fracture toughness of a *homogeneous* PMMA specimen of the same overall size. For more details see [13]. This testifies that the strength of the bond and becomes important in the discussion of the dynamic experiments presented below.

4.2. Results and discussion of dynamic crack growth experiments

The bimaterial specimens used in the dynamic experiments have a pre-cut edge notch of length 25mm along the interface. After the initiation event, the crack propagates dynamically along the interface. The bimaterial specimens are impact loaded in a drop weight tower (Dynatup-8100A). Intense stress waves generated by the impact and reflected by the specimen boundaries, load the notch tip up to crack initiation and the initiated crack propagates dynamically along the interface at speeds up to 900m/s. The transmission CGS technique in conjunction with high speed photography to record dynamic crack tip fields in a region approximately 50mm in diameter around the notch tip (only on the PMMA side of course). A rotating mirror, attached to a compressed air driven turbine shaft, is spun at high speed. The image is swept on a 35mm format film (Kodak TMAX-3200) that is fixed to a stationary drum. Discrete images corresponding to different stages of crack growth are formed by using a pulse laser as the light source. It is a Spectra-Physics Argon-ion pulse laser (model 166). Short pulses of 30ns duration produce sharp interference patterns during crack growth. The interval between successive light pulses is typically set at 1 μs for a total recording time of 80 μs . The system is triggered by a strain gauge on the specimen that senses the impact of the drop weight.

True symmetric loading cannot be achieved since it is extremely difficult to apply the impact load exactly on the interface. In addition since the wave speeds of PMMA and steel are vastly different, it the loading history at the crack tip would be completely different if the specimen were impacted on the PMMA or the steel side. Thus it was chosen to impact the specimen a small distance (7mm) into the steel side of the bond. A sequence of crack tip interference patterns ($\Delta=53\text{mm}$) are shown in figure 4. Time $t=0$ corresponds to the time of crack initiation.

When the crack initiates, intense stress waves emanate from the crack tip. These waves are visible in fig. 4 as discrete kinks in otherwise smooth fringes and as circular lines centered at points along the crack line. This observation is a reliable sign of a highly dynamic event. Indeed terminal velocities seem to be about 90% of the Rayleigh wave speed of PMMA, $c_R^{(1)}$, and in fact in some tests they have exceeded it (within experimental error). This observation was rather surprising given previous experience with dynamic crack growth in homogeneous PMMA specimens of the same configuration (max speeds about $0.35c_R$). Attributing such a phenomenon to the existence of a weak bond is not very convincing since our bond calibration suggests a bond at least as strong as PMMA. As result we believe that the reason for such high speeds is intimately related to the strong material properties mismatch between PMMA and steel. This mismatch is expected to produce a complicated mechanism of energy storage in the steel side and subsequent energy transfer to the PMMA.

Figure 4 : Sequence of high speed interferograms showing transient crack growth along a PMMA/steel bimaterial interface.

Figure 5 : Velocity and acceleration histories of above test.

Typical velocity and acceleration histories are shown in figure 5. Note that in this particular case there is a very large crack tip acceleration (approx. 10^7g , g : acceleration of gravity) immediately after the crack initiates. This would suggest that transient effects would be present close to initiation ($t=0$). As was mentioned earlier, the rate of change of the oscillatory index with time ($\dot{\epsilon}$) may be considered a partial measure of transience. For the same test as fig. 5 we have plotted ϵ and $\dot{\epsilon}$ versus time in figure 6. It is clear that at lower times even though ϵ does not vary a lot with velocity (see fig. 3), the acceleration high enough to result in a large $\dot{\epsilon}$. Let us now attempt to analyze the frame of fig. 4 at $t=10\mu s$. This corresponds to a local maximum value of $\dot{\epsilon}$ in this particular test. By digitizing the midpoints of fringes outside the near-tip three-dimensional zone

and by performing a least squares fit we can obtain the coefficients of either eq. (8) or the gradient of eq. (9). The result of such a fit for the K -dominant field of Yang, Suo and Shih (eq. (8)) is shown in figure 7a. The squares are digitized data points from the interferogram at $t=10\mu s$. The solid line is the quantity $\partial(\hat{\sigma}_{11} + \hat{\sigma}_{22})/\partial x_1$ calculated numerically by using the results for K from the fitting procedure generated by the same data points. As can be clearly seen eq. (8) cannot represent the data to any reasonable extent. The deformation of field of this particular picture therefore is nowhere near K -dominant. In fact the main feature which is the fact that the fringes approaching the crack tip seem to be parallel near the interface, cannot be captured at all by eq.(8). Similar results were seen when fitting eq. (8) to other interferograms, even in regions where ε was not changing very rapidly, even though in the later case the fit was somewhat better.

Figure 6 : ε and $\dot{\varepsilon}$ as functions of time in a typical test.

The result of the fit of the transient higher order field of Liu, Rosakis and Lambros [5] is shown in figure 7b. The data points are exactly the same as before and the solid line is the result of the fit. Clearly the fit is very good over a large area of the specimen. All features of the field are successfully captured by eq. (9). This shows that the K -dominant analysis cannot be used for cases where accelerations are high (which seems to be the norm for dynamic interfacial crack propagation, at least for short times after initiation.). Use of a transient analysis is absolutely necessary if fracture parameters such as K are to be known with confidence. We are currently in the process of analyzing a multitude of dynamic experiments using eq. (9).

Figure 7 : Fit of asymptotic field to data fringe points for (a) K -dominant field and (b) transient higher order field.

5. DYNAMIC EXPERIMENTS ON COMPOSITE PLATES

As a continuation of our work on the dynamic fracture of bimaterial systems, we have started investigating the unstable failure of thick fiber reinforced polymeric composite laminates. The composite plates will be subjected to in- and out-of-plane impact loading, and real time high speed CGS interferograms will be taken on one or both of the plate surfaces. Two proposed loading geometries are shown in figure 8a,b. For the CGS technique to be light efficient, a specularly reflective surface is required. thus these laminates have to have very small surface roughness ($<1\mu\text{m}$). This in itself is a considerable achievement on laminate fabrication.

Figure 8 : Two proposed geometries for impact of thick laminate composites

It is hoped that the coupling of real time images along with postmortem examination of the fractured specimens will lead to conclusive results about the damage evolution and mechanisms (in particular ply delamination) active during the event of dynamic fracture of thick composites.

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